

Sustainability Management Simulation: Net Zero

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Keywords

Business, Climate-change Education, Economics, Environmental Management, Hospitality Management, Stakeholder Management, Strategic Decision-making, Sustainability

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Sustainability Management Simulation: Net Zero* (Sim Institute). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The *Sustainability Management Simulation: Net Zero* (see Figure 1) is designed for students at all levels to experience the challenges and opportunities of reducing corporate greenhouse gas emissions in line with the objectives of the Paris Agreement while managing business performance. In the simulation, participants play the role of a hotel manager tasked with reducing the hotel's greenhouse gas emissions by 50 percent over 7 years. Each year, students choose up to three initiatives that can help reduce the hotel's emissions and determine the level of spending on staff training and guest awareness communication. At the end of 7 years, students need to have reduced the hotel's emissions by 50 percent, and cumulative emissions should not have exceeded the hotel's total greenhouse gas emissions budget for the game. At the same time, emission-reduction efforts should not come at the expense of profitability.

Net Zero was developed by Tim Rogmans of the Sim Institute and published by Harvard Business Publishing in March 2022. The simulation was updated in 2024. A Spanish language version was published in 2023, and AI-generated feedback was incorporated in 2025.

Facts

Release date:	2022
Developer:	Tim Rogmans, Sim Institute
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	1–1000
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	60 minutes
Languages:	English, Spanish
Environment:	Laptop or PC with internet access
Material:	Brief & debrief slides, along with teaching notes, are available. Simulation includes one tab with the required information on climate change.
Price:	\$16.25 per student for academic use. \$47.95 per participant for corporate use. Facilitator materials provided free of charge.

Resonance & Criticism

Net Zero won the Gold Medal at the 2022 Serious Play Awards in the Higher Education category. It was also Highly Commended in the FT Responsible Business Education Awards.

It has been used by over 50,000 learners worldwide. Most users are university students, though companies also use the simulation for corporate training and sustainability planning.

The reception has generally been positive, and there have been no strong or consistent points of criticism. There have been some user observations relevant to enhancing the simulation's success. For example, it has been mentioned that students need adequate time to play the simulation.

Game Principle & Process

In the simulation, students learn that there is a business case for emissions reduction, as illustrated by Bhattacharya and Polman (2017), Polman and Winston (2021), and Topping (2019). These and other studies have argued that emissions reductions and improvements in financial performance (lower costs, higher revenues, and lower risk) can go hand in hand.

As a direct illustration of this concept in the hospitality industry, Rogmans (2022) has written a case study on the emissions-reduction efforts of IHG Hotels & Resorts, which served to validate and refine the simulation. These studies are examples from a growing body of literature that underpins the simulation.

In Net Zero, students manage a successful 4-star hotel located in one of five cities. At the start of the game, the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are in the same range as other 4-star hotels in the city, and there is a lot of opportunity to improve sustainability performance.

The hotel must reduce its GHG emissions by 50% over the next seven years while staying within its carbon budget and optimizing financial performance. Each year, students are presented with a set of initiatives that can help lower the hotel's emissions. Purchasing carbon offsets is not an option in the simulation. The initiatives fall into three categories: energy, purchasing, and management, and up to three can be selected per year. After entering their choices in the Decisions section, participants review the outcomes in the Dashboard before moving on to the next year to make new decisions.

The simulation can be played individually or in teams.

Net Zero is supported by explanations of emissions and climate change, including a glossary of terms.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The central learning objective is for students to experience the opportunities and challenges related to corporate emissions reductions. By playing Net Zero, participants will learn that making significant cuts in greenhouse gas emissions is challenging for companies but possible. Students learn that reducing emissions does not need to go at the expense of business performance and can, in fact, help to reduce costs and increase revenues (i.e., there is a business case for sustainability).

Related learning objectives include that choosing emission reduction strategies requires managers to think through all the consequences of their decisions and to prioritize. Not all initiatives that look "green" have a significant impact on emissions. Finally, corporate emission-reduction efforts benefit from employee, customer, and supplier involvement, and sustainability performance measurement and analysis are critical to achieving results.

The teacher's role can be broken down into three phases: the brief, play, and debrief.

In the brief, the teacher can recap climate change information and explain the game mechanics. This can be provided by watching the student video, using the brief slides, or playing the simulation in front of students for one round. When playing in teams, the teacher needs to assign students to teams in the facilitator interface.

The instructor has various resources available to support the simulation, including briefing and debriefing slides, as well as a teaching note that explains the learning objectives, teaching strategies, and details of the underlying model. Instructors will benefit from trying the simulation before using it in class, but there is no need to be an expert in every aspect of it.

During play, the teacher should not interfere; only help students who are stuck or have issues they can't solve on their own. The teacher can follow student progress on the Class Results page in the facilitator interface.

The debrief can start with a general discussion of the student experience, followed by a review of the leaderboard and a discussion of decisions made and results obtained by students or teams. Details of all simulation runs are available to teachers. The debrief slides can help guide and structure the discussion and consolidate critical learning points.

Effectiveness

To date, there have been no scientific studies or surveys of the simulation's effectiveness. Evidence of improved student engagement and learning outcomes is, so far, only anecdotal, coming from educators around the world who have provided feedback and continue to use the simulation in their classes.

Typical comments from educators include: "I simulated my programme. It is excellent.", "It helped surface many issues we were discussing practically and tangibly and brought the discussion to life.", and "The videos, teaching notes, and deck were superb."

A critical feature of the simulation is that the level of difficulty can be matched to students' skill sets. This can be done by changing settings in the facilitator section and by including or excluding topics that may be challenging for some students (e.g., emissions by scope, carbon budget, cash flow).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The simulation's difficulty level is high, partly to reflect reality and partly to help students learn that a target for emissions reduction inevitably involves an arbitrary element.

The simulation is available in English and Spanish. Online translation tools have worked well in a variety of languages.

The simulation assumes that the evidence for climate change is objective and then focuses on how best to reduce corporate emissions. People who believe that emissions reduction is unnecessary may have issues with the simulation. However, students concerned about the costs of emissions reduction can learn that cost-effective methods are available.

The simulation has been developed according to WCAG 2.1 AA accessibility standards.

Reviewer(s): Elisabeth Johnston, Birgit Zürn

Sources

- Bhattacharya, C. B., & Polman, P. (2017). Sustainability lessons from the front lines. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 58(2), 71–78.
- Polman, P., & Winston, A. (2021). The net positive manifesto. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2021/09/the-net-positive-manifesto>
- Rogmans, T. (2022). *Sustainability Management Simulation: Net Zero* (Teaching note).
- Rogmans, T. (2022). *IHG Hotels & Resorts: Reducing emissions in a decade of business expansion* (Case No. 322-0251-1). The Case Centre.
- Topping, N. (2019, June 21). Is your company ready for a zero-carbon future? *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2019/06/is-your-company-ready-for-a-zero-carbon-future>